

SOCIAL SCIENCES IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE SECOND WORLD WAR: ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

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During the war years, science and research activities in Uzbekistan were intensively continued. Educational institutions and research institutes relocated as a result of the evacuation made a significant contribution to the development of science in the republic. Despite the fact that it was a time of war, the rapid and positive reforms that were implemented stimulated development in the field of social sciences as well as in all branches of science. The establishment of the Academy of Sciences in the republic served to increase this process more consistently.

UzFAN (Uzbek branch of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR) Institute of Language, Literature and History was established in 1940 on the basis of the Institute of Language and Literature of the Science Committee. The best qualified personnel of the republic were attracted to the new institute. The scope of his scientific activity has been expanded, and as a result, the content and style of the institute's scientific activity has also expanded. The institute has set itself the goal of studying a number of current problems in the language, literature and history of the Uzbek people. In August 1941, about the publication of a number of Alisher Navoi's works and the translation of his selected lyrics, and Professor A.Y. A special decision was made to publish Yakubovsky's work "On the issue of the ethnogenesis of the Uzbek people". In the study of Alisher Navoi's works, the services of Mirza Abdulla Nasriddinov, recognized as a connoisseur of Navoi's works, should be highlighted. In particular, this institution has carried out several works on the compilation of Russian-Uzbek and Uzbek-Russian concise and fully annotated dictionaries. These dictionaries, published in 1942, were highly appreciated by the scientific community.

The work of developing the grammar of the current Uzbek language, Uzbek-Russian, Russian-Uzbek dictionaries and the explanatory dictionary of Alisher

Navoi was continued. By the beginning of the 1943-1944 academic year, the textbook "Grammar of the Uzbek language for secondary school" was published.¹ Linguistic scientists studied the history of the Uzbek language (studied the preserved sources and manuscripts of the 11th - 19th centuries), worked out the grammar of the modern Uzbek language, scientifically described the dialects of the regions of Uzbekistan, created the index of the Uzbek language dictionary. they were engaged in filling, they studied the Karakalpak and Uyghur languages. Literary experts prepared a number of works of Uzbek classical literature for academic publication (Lutfiy, Bedil, Gulkhani).² Philological scientists conducted research in the field of literature and linguistics. Corresponding member of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Professor E.E. A group of scientific employees of the institute under the leadership of Bertels was preparing for publication a collection dedicated to the history of Uzbek literature and classic Uzbek works. Folklorists collected materials about Uzbek folk tales and published popular pamphlets. Professor E.E. Bertels and Doctor of History I.P. Petrushevsky actively participated in the preparation of materials for the bibliographic dictionary of Central Asian poets, writers, scientists and statesmen who lived and created until the 19th century.³

By December 1943, under the leadership of professor A.K. Borovkov, a correspondent member of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, the scientific grammar of the Uzbek language was being prepared for publication at the Institute of Language and Literature.

Grammar is intended for students of higher educational institutions, Uzbek language teachers of secondary schools and researchers. A number of Uzbek scientists, in particular, doctor of philological sciences, professor A. Sa'diy, candidate of philological sciences, associate professor T. Salimov, doctor of philological sciences, professor A.V. The Mirtovs are involved. The publication of the scientific grammar of the Uzbek language in 1944 was emphasized by the group. Its size is 30 printed sheets.⁴

The Uzbek language network of the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan was resuming studies of Uzbek dialects. First of all, it is planned to continue the work of professor A.K. Borovkov, correspondent member of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, on the classification of Uzbek

¹ НАУз, ф. 1, оп. 1, д. 669, д. 46

² НАУз, ф. 1, оп. 1, д. 17, л. 56

³ Отчет о работе Академии наук СССР за 1944 г. М.; Л., 1944. С. 105

⁴ Правда Востока, 7 декабря 1943 г. № 250, ст-39

dialects. The institute is planning to create a special map of Uzbek dialects and provide general information about them based on available materials. At the same time, composite dialects of the Uzbek language are also being studied.⁵

Despite the war years, archaeological research was carried out on a broad front. In 1943, during the excavation of a large hill near Tashkent, the remains of an ancient fortress from the 4th century AD were found. S.P. The Khorezm archaeological expedition, which conducted excavations in the lower reaches of the Amudarya and Syrdarya under the leadership of Tolstov (later a correspondent member of the USSR FA), achieved interesting results. This expedition discovered a new "Su-Yargen" culture related to the "painted pottery culture" of South Turkestan, Iran and the Middle East.

More than 35 ancient graves of the III century AD were found during the excavations on the way of the Tashkent and Farhod canals. Excavations of a large border fortress in Syrdarya made it possible to trace the history of the seven-century (IV-XI) medieval culture of Uzbekistan. A cave city with a length of up to 6 km was discovered on the banks of the Kshtut River in the Penjikent region of Tajikistan, and large domed halls with the traces of burials of people from the Stone Age and animals depicted on the walls were also discovered.⁶

The archeological works carried out in Termiz, Samarkand, Khorezm, Fergana and Tashkent regions greatly enriched the archeology of Uzbekistan. As a result of these works, solutions were found to a number of very important fundamental questions related to the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan (the history of the primitive society in the territory of Uzbekistan, the periodization of the history of Uzbekistan, the history of irrigation in Uzbekistan).

During this period, the excavation and research of the tomb of Timurids in Samarkand was carried out. A lot of jewelry belonging to Syria, Iran and China was found in the graves. Also, excavation works were carried out in the observatory of Mirzo Ulugbek and palace structures in the garden of the medieval ruler outside the city, excavation works were carried out in the town of Afrosiyob and other objects. Excavations in the large border fortress in Syrdarya made it possible to trace the history of the seven-century (IV-XI centuries) medieval culture of Uzbekistan.⁷

⁵ Правда Востока, 8 декабря 1943 г. № 237, ст-47

⁶ Левшин Б. В. Советская наука в годы Великой Отечественной войны / АН СССР. Архив; Отв. Ред. Ким М. П. М.: Наука, 1983. С. 133

⁷ ААП РУз, ф. 58, оп. 1, д. 11, л. 18

Work on the preparation of the general work "History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan" has begun in the creative cooperation of Uzbek scientists with Russian scientists. Academician V.V. Struve and other well-known historians initiated the convening of a scientific meeting dedicated to the problem of ethnogenesis of Uzbeks and other peoples of Central Asia, and the materials of the meeting were of great importance in the preparation of this work.⁸ On the creation of "History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan" Y.G. Gulumov, V.Y. Zohidov, M.E. Voronets, I.K. Dodonov, Kh.Sh. Inoyatov, Z.Sh. Rajabov, A.A. Semyonov, O.A. Sukhareva, R. Uygun, V.A. Shishkin and other Uzbek scientists worked. Together with them, K.V. Trevor, S.W. Bakhrushin, A.K. Borovkov, Y.V. Gauthier, P.P. Ivanov, M.V. Nechkina, V.I. Picheta, S.P. Tolstov, A.Y. Yakubovsky and other famous scientists of Russia were also active.⁹

On June 18, 1944, Academician Struve's scientific lecture on "History of the Peoples of Central Asia in the Newly Discovered Writings of Xerxes son of Darius" at the scientific meeting held at the Institute of History and Archeology of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR took place. The lecture aroused great interest in many people. The correspondent member of the Academy of Sciences, who took part in the debate, A.Y. Yakubovsky and senior researcher of the institute V.A. The Shishkins noted that Academician Struve's research sheds light on a number of ethnic problems of the peoples of Central Asia, in particular, that it determines the settlement boundaries of a number of ancient tribes.¹⁰

The team of the Leningrad Department of the Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR, located in Tashkent, completed the work of compiling the third volume of the history of Uzbekistan. The first two volumes were compiled by the Moscow team of the Institute of History during their stay in Tashkent in 1941-1943. The first volume was published under the editorship of Academician Struve, and the second volume was published under the editorship of Bahrushin, correspondent member of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR.

The third volume prepared under the editorship of Pankratova, a correspondent member of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR, is dedicated to the Soviet period of Uzbekistan and covers the events until July 1944. In addition to the scientific staff of the Leningrad and Moscow departments of the Institute of History of the USSR

⁸ Ахунова М.А., Лунин Б. В. История исторической науки в Узбекистане. Краткий очерк. Ташкент, 1970. С. 124

⁹ Садыков А. Рожденная в войну // Звезда Востока. 1975. № 12. С. 124

¹⁰ Правда Востока, 18 июня 1944 года № 119 (6474), ст-18

Academy of Sciences, Tashkent scientists also participated in the work of compiling the history of Uzbekistan.¹¹

Historical-philosophical issues took an important place in the research of Uzbek scientists. Great attention was paid to the study of the history of socio-philosophical and natural-scientific thinking of the peoples of Central Asia. In particular, Professor T.N. Rainov's work is dedicated to the life and work of the greatest scientists of the Middle Ages - Farabi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Khorezmi. The great scientist of Uzbekistan I.M. Mominov made a significant contribution.¹²

It should be said that in these years, the concept of the historical development of the peoples of the East, which was against the widespread Eurocentrism in Western historical-philosophical literature and Oriental studies, was founded. It is known that the political condition of Eurocentrism was to justify and justify the colonial system of the Western countries, to justify it with the civilizational mission of the West in the backward countries of the East. S.P., an honorary academician of the Uzbek Academy of Sciences, overthrew Eurocentrism. Tolstov has a special place, he conducted research on this topic long before the works of Edward Said¹³ and others. In revealing the baselessness of Eurocentrism, S.P. One of the most important achievements of the Tolstov expedition was the discovery and study of primitive settlements located around the Amudarya and Syrdarya deltas, in the Southern Aral Sea, as well as in Sarikamish Bay.

S.P. Tolstov exposed the baselessness of the idea of Eurocentrism and proved that the style of domed buildings, widely used in world architecture, first appeared in the lands of Ancient Khorezm and passed through Parthia to Rome. S.P. One of the most important finds of Tolstov in the Koyqrylan fortress was the ancient Khorezm inscription.¹⁴

Although the difficult conditions of the wartime complicated the work of archaeologists, they could not stop it. In 1944-1945 intensive research work was carried out in Varakhsha settlement in Bukhara region, in 1945 S.P. Under the leadership of Tolstov and Y. Ghulomov, the activity of the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition of the USSR Academy of Sciences was revived. As a result of the long-term activity of the expedition, which began in 1937, many

¹¹ Правда Востока, 25 июля 1944 года. № 145(6500), ст-46

¹² Узбекская ССР в годы Великой Отечественной войны (1941–1945 гг.). Т. III. Победоносное завершение войны. С. 162

¹³ Said, Edward W. Orientalism. New York: Random House, 1978

¹⁴ Толстов С. П. Древний Хорезм. –М.: Наука, 1948. С. 210

archaeological monuments of antiquity were found and studied, and valuable materials related to the irrigation history of the Khorezm oasis were obtained.

During the Second World War, Tashkent became the center of research in the field of oriental studies, which required the expansion of scientific oriental studies and the training of qualified orientalists. This caused the issuance of a special decision (August 1944) by the Central Asian Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union and the Soviet of Ministers of the USSR on the restoration of the Faculty of Oriental Studies of the Central Asian State University. In the conditions of the severe war in the republic, many Russian orientalists continued their scientific activities with determination and efficiency: A.P. Barannikov, A.M. Belenitsky, V.I. Belyaev, V.M. Beskrovny, A.K. Borovkov, E.E. Bertels, I.N. Binnikov, A.M. Dyakov, A.N. Kononov, N.D. Mikluho-Maclay, O.I. Smirnova, I.P. Petrushevskiy, K.B. Starkova, N.V. Pigulevskaya, V.V. Struve, A.S. Tveritinova, K.V. Trevor, A.L. Troitskaya, D.I. Tikhonov, A.Y. Yakubovsky and others shared their experience and knowledge with their Uzbek colleagues.

The science of oriental studies in Uzbekistan developed significantly, especially after the establishment of the Institute for the Study of Oriental Manuscripts of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan in January 1944 (on the basis of the Oriental Department of the State Public Library of Uzbekistan).¹⁵

Before the beginning of the scientific activity of the institute, its funds contained 6102 volumes of manuscripts and about 6 thousand lithographic books.¹⁶ With the study and scientific description of Eastern manuscripts, the employees of the Institute D.G. Voronkovskiy, A. Rasulov, B. Zahidkhanov, E. Muhammedkhojayev and others were successfully involved.¹⁷ According to the official documents, "the fact that a large part of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR was in Tashkent gave an impetus to strengthen the work of the Institute of Central Asian Studies." In order to support this opinion, professor A.A. Semyonov's works on Central Asian source studies in the 16th century and the history of the Kokan Khanate in the first half of the 19th century are mentioned.¹⁸

¹⁵ О работе Института по изучению восточных рукописей // Известия Академии наук Узбекской ССР. Ташкент, 1950. № 1. С.119-120

¹⁶ Ахунова М. А., Лунин Б. В. История исторической науки в Узбекистане. С. 104

¹⁷ О работе Института востоковедения АН УзССР // Известия Академии наук Узбекской ССР. Ташкент, 1951. № 5. С. 114–117

¹⁸ Отчет о работе Академии наук СССР за 1944 г. М.; Л., 1944. С. 336

The rapid development of scientific research led to the establishment of the Institute of History and Archeology in November 1943.

In October 1944, the Institute of History of Material Culture under the FA of the USSR, in cooperation with the State Museum of Fine Arts, included M.M. Gerasimov (sculptor-anthropologist) and archaeologist V.N. He will send a special expedition with Cherensova to Uzbekistan. The expedition will study the rock paintings of the primitive community found in the Kohitang mountains. Such drawings are found for the first time in Central Asia, their study is of great scientific interest. They can provide new materials about the life and art of primitive man. In necessary cases, the expedition is expected to carry out archaeological excavations.¹⁹

Ethnographic studies. At the beginning of 1942, most of the employees of the Institute of Ethnography of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR, who survived the first winter of the blockade, were evacuated to Central Asia, mainly to Tashkent, where they began their activities as a group of Tashkent ethnographers.²⁰ This group managed to start intensive scientific activity in 1942, despite the difficulties associated with the evacuation and organizational period. Problems related to the study of the ethnic composition and ethnography of the peoples of Central Asia were developed.²¹

In 1942, S.P. Tolstov was appointed director of the Institute of Ethnography, which became the country's leading ethnographic institute. Each of the three groups of the institute focused on certain problems. First of all, the Moscow group was assigned the task of studying the problems related to the ethnic situation in the war zone. The Tashkent group, which participated in these studies, also developed issues of ethnography of Central Asia and some other regions of the USSR. The task of establishing ethnographic fieldwork in Central Asia was also set.

In 1943-1944, the Tashkent group became a center of scientific research not only in ethnography, but also in a number of related disciplines. A.D. The commission on ethnogenesis under the history and philosophy department of the USSR Academy of Sciences headed by Udalov was sent to the Tashkent group of the Institute of Ethnography of the Union Academy. In addition, a group developing maps of nations was included in the Tashkent group.

¹⁹ Правда Востока, 4 октября 1944 г. № 194, ст-59

²⁰ Марков Г. Е. Советские этнографы в годы Великой Отечественной войны // СЭ. 1985. № 2. С. 23–35

²¹ Архив Института этнологии и антропологии имени Н. Н. Миклухо-Маклая Российской Академии наук (далее – АИЭА), д. 10, л. 2

Thus, the scientific and research work carried out by the UZFA, scientific staff and researchers of existing research institutes, scientists of higher educational institutions, helped to further improve social science networks in the republic. During the war years, scientific achievements in areas considered important for social sciences were widely applied and as a result of them, development of these fields was stimulated in the republic.

REFERENCES:

1. ААП РУз, ф. 58, оп. 1, д. 11, л. 18
2. Ахунова М. А., Лунин Б. В. История исторической науки в Узбекистане. С. 104
3. Левшин Б. В. Советская наука в годы Великой Отечественной войны / АН СССР. Архив; Отв. Ред. Ким М. П. М.: Наука, 1983. С. 133
4. Марков Г. Е. Советские этнографы в годы Великой Отечественной войны // СЭ. 1985. № 2. С. 23–35
5. НАУз, ф. 1, оп. 1, д. 17, л. 56
6. Отчет о работе Академии наук СССР за 1944 г. М.; Л., 1944. С. 105
7. О работе Института востоковедения АН УзССР // Известия Академии наук Узбекской ССР. Ташкент, 1951. № 5. С. 114–117
8. О работе Института по изучению восточных рукописей // Известия Академии наук Узбекской ССР. Ташкент, 1950. № 1. С.119-120
9. Правда Востока, 25 июля 1944 года. № 145(6500), ст-46
10. Толстов С. П. Древний Хорезм. –М.: Наука, 1948. С. 210
11. Садыков А. Рожденная в войну // Звезда Востока. 1975. № 12. С. 124
12. Узбекская ССР в годы Великой Отечественной войны (1941–1945 гг.). Т. III. Победоносное завершение войны. С. 162
13. Якубовский А. Ю. К вопросу об этногенезе узбекского народа. Ташкент: Фан, 1941. С. 3–19; См. также: РГАСПИ, ф. 17, оп. 22, д. 276, л. 10
14. Said, Edward W. Orientalism. New York: Random House, 1978
15. Saidolimov S., Rahimov M., Sagdullayev K., Nazarov R., Babadjanov X. O‘zbek xalqining fashizm ustidan qozonilgan g‘alabaga qo‘shgan hissasi, kitob-albom, Toshkent, “O‘zbekiston”, 2020. 189-bet